

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SENSORY GROUNDING TECHNIQUES ON ANXIETY LEVELS AMONG STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Background: Anxiety is a common psychological challenge among undergraduate students and post graduate students, often triggered by academic workload, performance pressure, socializing and clinical responsibilities. Anxiety can impair concentration, memory, and motor coordination, negatively affecting academic success. Sensory grounding techniques, which engage the five senses to anchor individuals in the present moment, will emerged as a simple, non-invasive strategy to reduce anxiety symptoms.

Aim: To evaluate the effectiveness of sensory grounding techniques on anxiety levels among students.

Methodology: After receiving ethical approval by the institution ,A quasi-experimental pre-test and post-test design will be conducted at Dr. D.Y. Patil College of Physiotherapy, Pimpri, Pune. A purposive sample of 89 undergraduate and postgraduate students will be recruited. Anxiety levels will be assessed using the Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HAM-A) and Beck Anxiety Inventory (BAI). Participants will undergo a structured sensory grounding intervention, including the 5-4-3-2-1 method. Post-intervention scores will be compared with baseline measures.

Discussion: The present study examined the effect of the intervention by comparing pre-test and post-test scale scores of the same participants. The findings will indicate a clear improvement in post-test scores compared to pre-test scores, suggesting that the treatment will have a positive impact on the measured outcome. The effect size analysis will demonstrate a meaningful magnitude of change, suggesting that the treatment effect is not only statistically significant but also practically relevant.

Keywords: Anxiety, Sensory Grounding, Students, Anxiety Management, Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale, Beck Anxiety Inventory

INTRODUCTION-Anxiety is a prevalent emotional response experienced by individuals in high-pressure environments, such as health professional education. It is characterized by excessive worry, tension, and physiological reactions in anticipation of perceived threats or challenges (1).

In educational settings, particularly within health sciences, students often face various academic stressors that can trigger anxiety. Higher secondary and undergraduate students, in particular, are especially susceptible to anxiety, as they must juggle demanding performance expectations, heavy academic workloads, and responsibilities related to learning outcomes (2). The primary objective of higher secondary and undergraduate education is to cultivate academic skills, psychomotor abilities, and reasoning capacity. Students are required to master a broad array of subjects, ranging from anatomy and pathology to advanced theoretical and practical techniques, while also engaging in experiential learning that involves direct application of knowledge (3). This transition from classroom learning to real-world application often brings significant psychological stress. Additionally, factors such as performance evaluations, extensive study sessions, and the fear of making errors can further elevate students' anxiety levels (4). If left unaddressed, chronic anxiety can negatively impact academic performance, hinder cognitive function, reduce concentration, and obstruct the learning of new skills (5).

In recent years, the focus has shifted from merely identifying anxiety to exploring effective psychological strategies for alleviating it. Grounding techniques have gained attention as a straightforward and effective approach to reducing anxiety symptoms (6). By shifting focus from upsetting internal experiences (such as racing thoughts, panic, or anxiety) to external or sensory inputs, grounding refers to psychological techniques that help people "ground" or anchor themselves in the here and now (7). This technique aids individuals in regaining control during anxiety episodes and helps them detach from harmful emotional cycles.

Grounding techniques can be categorized into three main types: sensory grounding, physical grounding, and mental grounding. Sensory grounding aims to engage the five senses to draw attention to immediate sensations. For example, one might identify five visible objects, four tactile items, three sounds, two scents, and one taste. Physical grounding techniques, such as feeling the floor underfoot, stretching, or holding an object, help individuals reconnect with the physical world. Mental grounding involves redirecting thoughts through cognitive exercises, such as counting backward, describing the surroundings, or repeating calming phrases (8)(9).

These techniques are straightforward to practice, require no special tools, and can be used wherever needed, making them highly suitable for students who may suddenly feel anxious or panicked (10). Research from the Cleveland Clinic (11) has shown that grounding activates the senses and calms the amygdala, the brain's fear centre, helping alleviate stress and anxiety. Another study found that sensory grounding exercises, such as the "5-4-3-2-1 method," led to noticeable reductions in the physical symptoms of anxiety in participants dealing with acute stress (12).

For higher secondary and undergraduate students facing demanding academic pressures, grounding can serve as a valuable strategy for self-regulation. A quasi-experimental study focused on nursing students revealed that those who practiced grounding therapy experienced a significant decrease in both mild and moderate anxiety, and more students reported feeling free of anxiety afterward (13). The results highlighted improvements in breathing control, refocusing, and managing exam-related stress (14).

Although existing studies are promising, there is little research specifically addressing higher secondary and undergraduate students. These programs involve both academic rigor and emotional challenges linked to performance and future career preparation. Anxiety can negatively affect motor coordination, focus, and reasoning, which are fundamental skills for academic success (15). This suggests that integrating grounding practices into higher secondary and undergraduate education could help students better cope with anxiety and enhance their academic capabilities (16).

Additionally, grounding fits well with holistic education approaches, which promote psychological health, self-understanding, and emotional regulation. Unlike medications, grounding is a non-invasive, free, and efficient technique that can easily become part of everyday routines or school-based wellness programs (17).

Given the rise in student mental health concerns since the pandemic, there's renewed interest in wider adoption of grounding techniques (18). The COVID-19 pandemic increased anxiety among students owing to unpredictability, remote learning, and limited peer interaction (19). A recent survey of higher secondary and undergraduate students in India found that more than half reported moderate to high anxiety connected to academic uncertainty (20).

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

Aim

To evaluate the effectiveness of sensory grounding techniques on anxiety levels among students.

Objectives

- Understand how anxious students feel before the intervention using the Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HAM-A).
- Introduce and guide students through a structured sensory grounding routine.
- Measure any changes in anxiety levels after the intervention.

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

Study Design

A quasi-experimental design using pre-test and post-test assessments.

Study Setting

School and college.

Target Population

Higher secondary and Undergraduate students enrolled.

Sampling Method

Purposive sampling-students who are available and willing to participate.

The sample size was calculated using WINPEPI software (version 11.6). Assuming a 95% confidence level and an acceptable difference of 7%, the minimum required sample size for the study was estimated to be 89 participants. Therefore, the final sample size was fixed at 89.

Sample size=89

Inclusion Criteria

- Willing to participate voluntarily
- Not undergoing psychiatric treatment

Exclusion Criteria

- Students diagnosed with anxiety disorders and on medication
- Those with prior experience using grounding techniques

Materials Required

- Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HAM-A).
- Beck anxiety inventory
- Grounding technique guide (e.g., 5-4-3-2-1 method)
- Consent forms

- Data collection sheets or software

Outcome measures: -

Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HAM-A)

Overview of HAM-A

- **Developed by:** Max Hamilton in 1959.
- **Purpose:** To assess the severity of a patient's anxiety symptoms
- **Format:** Clinician-administered questionnaire with **14 items**
- **Scoring:** Each item is rated on a scale from **0 (not present)** to **4 (very severe)**

Structure of the 14 Items.

HAM-A evaluates both **psychic** and **somatic** symptoms of anxiety:

1. **Psychic Anxiety** (mental/emotional symptoms)

- Anxious mood (worry, anticipation of the worst)
- Tension (restlessness, inability to relax)
- Fears (of dark, strangers, being alone, animals, etc.)
- Insomnia (difficulty falling or staying asleep)
- Intellectual (difficulty concentrating, memory issues)
- Depressed mood (loss of interest, hopelessness)

2. **Somatic Anxiety** (physical symptoms)

- Muscular (aches, twitching, stiffness)
- Sensory (tingling, tinnitus, blurred vision)
- Cardiovascular (palpitations, chest pain)
- Respiratory (tight chest, choking feeling)
- Gastrointestinal (nausea, vomiting, diarrhoea)
- Genitourinary (frequency, urgency, menstrual issues)
- Autonomic (dry mouth, sweating, dizziness)
- Behaviour at interview (fidgeting, pacing, facial tension)

Scoring and Interpretation

- **Maximum score:** 56

PROCEDURE

Ethical approval

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Participated recruitment

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Informed consent (oral, written forms)

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Baseline anxiety assessment Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HAM-A)

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Sensory grounding education (structured teaching)

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Grounding technique (using implementation)

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Post-intervention anxiety assessment using Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HAM-A)

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Data analysis

RESULT

To be compiled after the intervention. Will include graphs, tables, and statistical analysis to show changes in anxiety levels.

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